

IPBES BBA Chapter 3 –Review of cross-sector biodiversity impact estimates (V1) / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (3.2)

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1. Description

This data management report presents a non-systematic literature review to examine cross-sector biodiversity impact estimates. This review specifically sought instances where biodiversity impacts of two or more sectors were estimated comparatively using a consistent approach. This review acknowledges key limitations, such as:

- The likelihood that certain ISIC-classified sectors receive greater attention than others.
- The assumptions involved in impact estimation (e.g., scope, attribution).
- The inconsistent ISIC sectoral classification in biodiversity impact assessments.

Despite these limitations, the review aims to identify economic sectors most frequently linked to significant biodiversity impacts and summarize methodologies employed in cross-sectoral comparisons.

2. Process Overview

3. Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Non-systematic literature review guided by the project leader and independent reviewer feedback.
- **Search language:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar (peer-reviewed & grey literature)
- **Search Date:** December 2023; repeated during December 2024

4. Review process

4.1. Collection of biodiversity assessment approaches to review

A non-systematic review was conducted using structured search strings in Google Scholar. The search strategy combined synonyms for:

- 'Biodiversity' / 'Nature'
- 'Impacts' / 'Dependencies'
- 'Assessment' / 'Evaluation'
- 'Sector' / 'Economy'

Due to the high number of search results (often in the thousands), a full review of all entries was not conducted. Instead, it was assumed that the most relevant results would appear first. The review continued until an entire page or more of results no longer met the inclusion criteria.

Results were filtered progressively by:

- **Title Screening:** To remove irrelevant results.
- **Abstract Screening:** To ensure relevance based on impact comparison criteria.
- **Full-Text Review:** To confirm the inclusion of quantitative & comparable impact estimates across multiple sectors.

4.2. Inclusion & exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Studies containing quantitative and comparable biodiversity impact estimates.

- Studies assessing two or more economic sectors.

Exclusion criteria:

- Studies examining only one sector (e.g., agriculture only, food products only).
- Studies providing qualitative impact estimates only.
- Studies using non-biodiversity metrics (e.g., CO₂ emissions, water use) without biodiversity relevance.

4.3. Snowball search from reference lists

Once key sources were identified, additional studies were retrieved checking cited references to locate further cross-sectoral assessments. The same inclusion/exclusion criteria were applied with no constraints on whether the additional source came from the peer-reviewed or grey literature.

5. Data extraction & classification

Given the diversity of methodologies and metrics used across studies, a normalization approach was applied:

- Sector classification: All economic sectors were reclassified into ISIC sector categories for consistency.
- Impact normalization: Biodiversity impact values were scaled relative to the highest impact sector in each study.
- Impact categories: Impacts were classified into:
 - Lower Impact (~0.00-0.25)
 - Medium Impact (~0.25-0.50)
 - Higher Impact (~0.50-1.00)

Assumptions & Limitations:

- Uncertainty bounds were not included in the analysis.
- Where multiple sectors were combined during the reclassification reclassified into the ISIC sectors, impacts should be considered in the highest impact category relevant.

6. Revisiting the search

Following the initial review (December 2023 - early 2024), the summary was submitted for the external review period as part of the IPBES process. Reviewers recommended additional sources, prompting a second search iteration using the same methodology to capture newly published studies. In total 31 key sources were used for data extraction and classification of impacts.

7. Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size (KB)	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_3.2_08-2025_(A)	CSV	3,67	List of 31 relevant sources identified